

Metadata description for archival material

Title: Archival material from the EUI Historical Archives of the European Union, in Florence, Italy.

Description: Archival material from the EUI Historical Archives of the European Union. Documents from Mauro Cappelletti's collection. The MC fonds consists of the documents collected by Mauro Cappelletti, including university courses, correspondence, manuscripts and typewritten notes, conference proceedings and offprints.

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Publications on the material: Published at, e.g.,
<https://doi.org/10.1017/S1574019625100849>

Preservation of research data: The material will be stored at
<https://archives.eui.eu/en/fonds/277221?item=MC>